

ISO-15118 Manipulation for Field Calibration of DC Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment

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Abstract—The EU’s 2035 phaseout of CO₂-emitting cars is leading to a surge in Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment (EVSE) installations. Because these are measurement devices, they will need regular metrological checks. This paper focuses on the development and testing of a field calibration system for EVSEs, using a Man-In-The-Middle (MIM) approach to intercept and manipulate the communication between the EVSE and the Electric Vehicle (EV). The proposed approach aims to overcome the limitations of using a vehicle as a load by enabling arbitrary variations in the test current. This approach forces the EV to draw different current levels and to test the EVSE under several operating conditions. The work extends to the DC domain a methodology previously used for AC EVSEs. In particular, the paper describes a software emulation environment to test the high-level communication protocols between the EVSE and the EV, under controlled laboratory conditions. The test equipment was developed and tested at the University of Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”, Italy.

Index Terms—e-Mobility, Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment, Battery Electric Vehicle, calibration, power measurement, energy measurement, Protocol Hacking.

I. INTRODUCTION

The EU considers Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) vehicles a major pollution source. Despite recent growth in alternative fuel vehicle sales, Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs) and Plug-in Hybrids remain a small portion of the overall fleet. The EU’s ban on ICE cars aims to accelerate the shift to sustainable transport, necessitating reliable and accurate EV charging infrastructure to support widespread EV adoption [1], [2]. In this context, the Electric Vehicle Supply Equipments (EVSEs) play a crucial role. EVSEs, like traditional fuel dispensers, require periodic metrological verification. This paper focuses on the development of a field calibration system for EVSEs, extending to the DC EVSEs the approach already proposed for the AC charging systems. As detailed in [3], a field calibrator for AC charging stations has already been developed. This system modifies the low-level communication protocol (IEC-61851) between the vehicle and the charging

station [4] to force the systems to operate at a predefined current level. The novelty of this work lies in achieving the same result obtained in AC, also for DC charger calibration. However, the extension of this approach to the DC case requires the manipulation of high-level communication protocols, specifically ISO-15118 [5], which is mandatory for DC fast charging [6]. The necessity to hack the protocol stems from the need to vary the test current to assess the EVSE metering subsystem under different operating conditions. This is essential to verify the correct operation of the EVSE internal meter across the whole input range, as highlighted in [3]. This need is part of the broader objectives of the European project Met4EVCS (Metrology for Electric Vehicle Charging Systems), which aims to define standardized test protocols and establish a metrological infrastructure for EVCSs.

II. BACKGROUND AND STANDARDS

The landscape of communication between EVs and EVSE is characterized by a multitude of standards and protocols. IEC 61851-1 [4] defines a low-level communication that is used to negotiate the energy exchange, and is based on analog signals. However, ISO-15118 [5] introduces High-Level Communication (HLC), enabling new functionalities such as Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G), Smart Charging and Fast Charging (mode 4). In AC charging, the implementation of HLC is optional, while in DC charging is mandatory. This approach aims to implement smart communication between the EV, the EVSE and the upper management systems. The main protocols used are:

- DIN SPEC 70121: Supports only DC charging.
- CHAdeMO: Primarily used in Asia, also for DC charging.
- ISO15118: The most widely used, allowing both DC and AC charging, while supporting Plug&Charge and smart charging. OCPP: Manages the communication between charging stations and the central management system.

EVSEs vary in technology and standards. This research focuses on public, wired charging stations commonly found in

Fig. 1. Proposed system

locations like car parks. These stations must include a meter to accurately measure the energy dispensed for commercial transactions, thus requiring calibration similar to a wattmeter or energy meter. Depending on the station type, this could involve a single-phase or three-phase AC wattmeter or a DC meter, used for energy billing. In all cases, the voltage and current must be measured using an external reference instrument to determine measurement accuracy.

III. PROPOSED CALIBRATION METHOD

The proposed calibration approach builds upon the concept of using the EV as a load for the charging station under test (DUT - Device Under Test). Hence, assuming that a vehicle to be charged is available, the idea is to place a reference wattmeter between the charging station and the vehicle (see Figure 1). However, this extension is obtained by implementing a MIM (Man In the Middle) device that can manipulate the communication between the EV and the EVSE in order to perform tests at several current levels, in various operating conditions and, in general, according to a recognized test protocol. As mentioned above, a similar approach has been successfully implemented for AC chargers. The novelty of this work lies in achieving the same result for DC charger calibration using HLC protocols. Therefore, it will be necessary to manipulate the ISO-15118 protocol to implement the block diagram shown in Figure 3. The device placed in the middle requires an EV emulator to interface with the EVSE under test, and an EVSE emulator to interface with the EV (acting as the electrical load). A more in-depth study of the ISO-15118 standard is necessary for the implementation of both vehicle and EVSE emulators.

The ISO-15118 protocol, as explained in Figure 2, is split into several documents. ISO15118-1 contains the use cases, ISO15118-2 defines the messages and sequences, and ISO15118-3 the physical and datalink requirements. The ISO 15118 protocol ensures secure communication between the EV and the EVSE for tasks like authentication, authorization, and charging control. The protocol is based on the exchange of messages, which are transmitted through the CP line of the charging connector via a Power Line Communication (PLC) modem. The messages are defined using eXtensible Markup

Fig. 2. ISO 15118 Parts and OSI Layers

Language (XML) schemas, which ensures structured and valid data exchange. The messages are encoded using Efficient XML Interchange (EXI) to reduce the message size and improve communication efficiency. Communication is initiated once the charging cable is plugged in.

A. ISO-15118

The ISO-15118 protocol establishes a client-server connection where the EV is the client and the EVSE the server. The messages are exchanged through the charging cable, using the CP pin. As described in [4] and [3], the CP (Control Pilot) line is already used for basic communication, carrying a PWM (Pulse Width Modulation) signal at 1 kHz. The HomePlug GreenPHY standard PLC modem modulates the HLC link layer over the same CP line, using the sub-GHz frequency band, which provides a good balance between data rate and range, making it suitable for in-vehicle and charging infrastructure communication. Technically, GreenPHY uses Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) modulation, a robust technique that divides the available bandwidth into multiple orthogonal subcarriers, each carrying a portion of the data. This helps mitigate the effects of multipath propagation and frequency-selective fading, common challenges in PLC [7]. Furthermore, GreenPHY incorporates error correction mechanisms to enhance the reliability of data transmission in the presence of noise and interference on the power line.

The SLAC (Signal Level Attenuation Characterization) protocol uses measurements of signal attenuation over the physical layer (PLC) to identify connected devices [8].

Security is provided by TLS (Transport Layer Security), using certificates issued by the car manufacturer or by a Certificate Provisioning Service (CPS).

The calibration process involves intercepting and modifying the communication messages exchanged between the EV and EVSE.

B. MIM device

A block scheme of the realized MIM device is shown in Figure 3. In this diagram, the vehicle emulator connects to the EVSE under test, while the charging station emulator

Fig. 3. Proposed system block diagram

connects to the vehicle acting as a load. As soon as the vehicle starts the charging session, the vehicle emulator will start its own charging session. By controlling both the charging station and vehicle communication, it will be possible to negotiate the desired test current. Coordination between the vehicle emulator and the charging station emulator will be necessary. These two units, together with the coordination software, constitute the Device in the Middle for the HLC (see Figure 3).

By modifying the parameters related to the available current in the EVSE (e.g. the `ChargeParameterDiscoveryReq` message) or the instantaneous current requested by the EV (`EVTargetCurrent` present in the message `CurrentDemandReq-Res` in DC), the system can force the EV to draw the desired test current level. The calibration setup includes a reference wattmeter connected in series with the EVSE to measure the actual energy delivered during the test. In AC charging, the exchange of messages is simpler, while in DC is required to perform `CableCheck` and `PreCharge` steps before the `PowerDelivery` message. In DC, the messages `CurrentDemandReq-Res` replace the `ChargingStatusReq-Res` messages of AC, because the battery is charged by an external charger and the current must be controlled.

IV. MIM IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation of the proposed methodology requires a software framework capable of emulating both the EV and EVSE behaviors and managing the message exchange of the ISO-15118 protocol. *EVERest* [9], an open-source library part of the *Linux Foundation Energy*, was chosen for this task.

EVERest is a suitable choice as it enables the emulation of both the EV and EVSE, and it manages the message exchange for a controlled charging session.

A. *EVERest* Framework

The framework uses a modular architecture, where each module is responsible for a specific function. It provides a set of components for the implementation of the ISO-15118 protocol. *EVERest* employs a microservices architecture, using

the Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) protocol for Inter-Process Communication (IPC). MQTT's publish/subscribe pattern, along with its online available broker, facilitates message routing between publishers and subscribers. While MQTT is a lightweight messaging protocol typically designed for constrained devices and unreliable networks, often used in IoT applications, its adoption for local IPC within *EVERest*, though potentially surprising, offers considerable flexibility.

EVERest was chosen as the solution to implement emulators for several reasons:

- **Open Source:** It aligns with the research project's accessibility requirements and the European community's needs.
- **Compatibility:** It supports multiple communication standards, not just ISO-15118. *EVERest* is compatible with standards/protocols like OCPP 1.6 (all) / 2.0.1 / 2.1 (basics), ISO 15118-2 (AC+DC), DC-BiDi: SAE J2847/2, DIN SPEC 70121, IEC 61851 / SAE J1772, Sunspec, CCS1, CCS2, NACS/Tesla.
- **Hardware Availability:** There is ready-to-use hardware fully supported by the chosen software framework. *EVERest* is fully supported by hardware like the Yeti and Yak boards (see Figure 4).
- **Modular Architecture:** *EVERest* has a modular architecture with a configurable degree, allowing the selection of functionalities to include.

Using an existing package for implementing communication protocols offers several advantages compared to developing from scratch: it allows significant time and resource savings; being already tested and compliant with reference standards, it guarantees greater reliability; it offers support and updates for future developments and standard extensions. Moreover, it facilitates interoperability with other systems, reducing compatibility problems with various EV and EVSE producers. The framework provides several tools and features:

- **Docker:** *EVERest* utilizes Docker containers for managing the software components and dependencies [10].
- **Mosquitto:** An MQTT broker used for communication between *EVERest* modules.

Fig. 4. Yeti and Yak boards

- Node-RED: A visual programming tool for creating user interfaces and controlling the system. EVERest provides a default dashboard for monitoring and controlling the charging session [11].
- YAML: Configuration files written in YAML are used to define the EVERest modules and settings

The following modules were used for implementing the ISO-15118 protocol:

- `ev_board_support`: Provides support for a generic EV board. `ISO15118_ev`: Implements the ISO 15118 protocol for the EV side.
- `ev_slac`: Enables the SLAC (Signal Level Attenuation Characterization) communication required for ISO 15118-3. `powermeter`: Allows interfacing with a generic wattmeter.
- `PyEvJosev`: Implements high-level communication protocols such as ISO-15118, using Python. It also provides an interface to interact with the lower layers such as SLAC.
- `JsYetiSimulator`: Emulates an EVSE using javascript, it includes functionalities to simulate the behaviour of the contactor, the PWM signal, SLAC and the ISO15118 protocol.

The combination of these modules enables a complete simulation environment for testing ISO-15118 communication.

B. Software Implementation

The software implementation involves two main modules: the EV emulator and the EVSE emulator. The EV module simulates the behavior of an EV, while the EVSE module emulates the behavior of a charging station. These two modules has been put in communication with each other to simulate a charging session. This was done for testing and development purposes only, as in the final scheme in Figure 5 the EV Emulator will communicate with the EVSE under test, and the EVSE Emulator will communicate with the real EV to

be charged. The `PyEvJosev` module implements the high-level communication between EV and EVSE via ISO-15118. The `EvseV2G` module implements ISO-15118-2 for an AC or DC charging station, and includes security features.

EVERest includes example configurations for AC and DC EVSE and EV emulation in Software-in-the-Loop (SIL) mode. However, these configurations are designed for single-machine testing, which is unsuitable for this research. Our setup requires two separate EVERest instances running on different machines, each with its own HomePlug GreenPhy PLC modem, to communicate with both the EV and EVSE sides (as shown in Figure 6). Therefore, the emulators were modified to enable independent operation across separate machines. The communication between the two modules was tested using two separate Linux PCs, each running an instance of EVERest. These PCs were connected to a local network, and Wireshark was used to monitor message exchange.

The correct behavior was verified after solving some issues regarding MQTT messages. Some additional messages have to be published to enable the Energy Meter Simulator (Yeti simulator) and the related UI elements.

C. Software Related Issue

The implementation of the proposed system required reverse engineering the EVERest framework to identify and correct some malfunctions. The most relevant issues that needed to be addressed were three: the lack of a correct triggering for the ISO-15118 high level communication; a malfunction in the contactor control in the EVSE emulator; an incomplete connection of all the required topics for the energy meter and other functionalities in the user interface.

The HLC in real operating condition is triggered by the link ready signals, nevertheless, in the SIL environment, EVERest triggers this event by an MQTT message sent by the simulator's GUI (Graphic User Interface) using Node-Red. The correct message, along with its syntax, was identified by reverse engineering the framework.

The contactor issue has been located in the `iso_server.cpp` file. The program was hanging indefinitely, waiting for the contactor to close. This was due to the `JsYetiSimulator` simulating both EVSE and EV functionalities. Separating the EV side onto a different machine resulted in the loss of certain internal messages, causing the hang.

A MQTT bridge was added to selectively connect all the additional topics required to fix the contactor problem to simulate the power meter and other functionalities of the GUI.

The test setup consists of two separate EVERest instances, one emulating the EV and the other emulating the EVSE. A local Mosquitto broker was used for the MQTT communication between the two instances [12].

Wireshark [13] was used to capture and analyze the network traffic, including the messages exchanged through the PLC modem. The tests were performed by running the EV and the EVSE emulators on separate computers. The communication was initiated using the Node-RED interface, and the process was monitored through the log of each emulator. The tests

Fig. 5. EVSE field test equipment

Fig. 6. Final scheme

were performed in laboratory conditions, using a simulation of the energy meter, since the implementation of the hardware interface is not part of this work.

D. Cybersecurity Related Aspects

Communication between EVs and EVSEs is secured using encryption, specifically AES-CBC-128 (Advanced Encryption Standard - Cipher Block Chaining), with the encryption key exchanged via ECDH (Elliptic-curve Diffie–Hellman). While this encryption protects against "man-in-the-middle" attacks (someone with only the public keys cannot decrypt messages), it presents a significant challenge for the proposed calibration approach. Because the entire message flow is encrypted, selectively altering individual messages (e.g., ChargingStatusRes or ChargeParameterDiscoveryReq concerning current) is impossible without breaking the communication's integrity. Any modification invalidates the digital signature and the entire exchange. To overcome this, the proposed architecture

employs separate encrypted channels: the vehicle emulator communicates with the EVSE under test, and the charging station emulator communicates with the vehicle used as a load. This allows each emulator to manage its encryption independently, enabling manipulation of the desired charging parameters without compromising overall system security. Each emulator uses its own certificate and key pair, establishing secure communication with its respective counterpart, thus addressing the cybersecurity challenges.

E. Hardware Implementation

The Yeti and Yak boards (see Figure 4) produced by PIONIX are natively supported by the EVERest framework. The Yeti board is a three-phase power board designed for charging electric vehicles up to 22kW. It supports alternating current (AC) charging in compliance with IEC-61851-1/SAE J1772 standards [4], with options for automatic single-phase/three-phase switching. Yeti's onboard system includes Control Pilot

Fig. 7. Yeti and Yak boards acquired

(CP) signal generation and CP signal sampling in sync with pulse width modulation (PWM), a three-phase power switching relay, three-phase power measurement, phase rotation direction detection, overcurrent protection, a Ground-Fault Circuit Interrupter (GFCI) module, connectors for higher-level boards, Liquid Cristal Display (LCD), RS485/ModBus, and temperature sensors. It can operate in "high-level" or "low-level" control mode, also supporting the ISO15118 protocol, and evaluate direct current (DC) charging in a laboratory environment.

The Yak board is a higher-level control board based on the Raspberry Pi Compute Module 4 that can be used for both AC and DC electric vehicle charging stations. It features a connector for direct connection to the Yeti board and includes a PLC GreenPHY modem for HLC (high level charging) communication with the car, communication interfaces such as UART, RS485/ModBus, CAN bus, Ethernet, Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, USB and GPIO ports, operation with the EVerest framework, and a sunlight-readable capacitive touch display.

Two complete HW kits were acquired (see Figure 7), one for the EVSE emulator and the other for the EV emulator. The kit is designed to implement the EVSE side, but the hw schematic provides the possibility to disable PWM generation and use the signal as an input only. This way, it has been possible to use one of the Yak as an EV emulator. At the time of writing, the developed software has been deployed on the two hardware kits. However, testing under real operating conditions has not yet been performed due to the lack of a testable EVSE and an HLC-capable EV.

V. EXPERIMENTAL TESTS

The emulated charging session includes the following steps:

- Low-level communication via IEC-61851;
- SLAC protocol simulation to establish a physical connection for high-level communication;

- High-level communication via the ISO-15118 protocol. SDP messages exchange to select the proper ISO-15118 protocol;
- Messages related to authentication, authorization, and negotiation of charging parameters are exchanged.
- Once the parameters are agreed upon, the energy flow is enabled through the closing of the contactor.
- The charging session proceeds through the exchange of ChargingStatus messages.

The emulation was validated through a capture of the network packets, using Wireshark, during a DC charging session.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented the implementation of a system that emulates the ISO-15118 high-level communication protocol that allows to modify the communication among the EV and the EVSE with the aim of calibrating the EVSE on-field. It uses the Man-In-the-Middle, through which it intercepts and manipulates the high-level communication between the EV and the EVSE, in a way that the EV can be forced to draw a predefined level of current. The EVerest open source framework was used for developing the emulation software. Several issues in the open source implementation were fixed through reverse engineering, such as the correct triggering of the ISO 15118 communication; proper contactor control in the EVSE emulator; correct connection of all the required topics for the energy meter simulation.

The software implementation allowed the emulation of the ISO-15118 communication in both AC and DC charging sessions in a laboratory environment. The installation of the software deployment on embedded platforms is ongoing. Future works will include the validation of the proposed calibration system with real charging stations and EVs and the field testing. Future works will also explore the integration of a hardware interface for the power meter, and investigate the impact of power quality on the metrological performance of the charging stations.

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REFERENCES

- [1] E. Commission and D.-G. for Communication, *REPowerEU, joint European action for more affordable, secure and sustainable energy*. Publications Office of the European Union, 2022.
- [2] M. Parchomiuk, A. Moradewicz, and H. Gawiński, “An overview of electric vehicles fast charging infrastructure,” in *2019 Progress in Applied Electrical Engineering (PAEE)*, 2019, pp. 1–5.
- [3] A. D. Femine, D. Gallo, C. Iodice, C. Landi, and M. Luiso, “Evse metrological verification through iec 61851 protocol hacking,” in *2024 IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Automotive (MetroAutomotive)*, 2024, pp. 130–135.
- [4] IEC. (2010) Iec 61851-1 ed2.0: Electric vehicle conductive charging system - part 1: General requirements.
- [5] ISO/IEC. (2012) Iso/iec dis 15118-2: Road vehicles - vehicle to grid communication interface – part 2: Network and application protocol requirements.
- [6] L. Rubino, C. Capasso, and O. Veneri, “Review on plug-in electric vehicle charging architectures integrated with distributed energy sources for sustainable mobility,” *Applied Energy*, vol. 207, pp. 438–464, 2017, transformative Innovations for a Sustainable Future – Part II. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261917308358>
- [7] M. Rathinasabapathy and R. Nakkeeran, “Performance analysis of adaptive ofdm system for broadband power line network,” in *IEEE-International Conference On Advances In Engineering, Science And Management (ICAESM -2012)*, 2012, pp. 167–173.
- [8] ISO/IEC. (2012) Iso/iec dis 15118-3: Road vehicles - vehicle to grid communication interface – part 3: Physical and data link layer requirements.
- [9] [Online]. Available: <https://lfenergy.org/projects/everest/>
- [10] [Online]. Available: <https://www.docker.com/>
- [11] [Online]. Available: <https://nodered.org/>
- [12] [Online]. Available: <https://mosquitto.org/>
- [13] [Online]. Available: <https://www.wireshark.org/>